

WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND EMPLOYEE OUTCOMES: A MULTICULTURAL STUDY IN GHANA

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Abstract

This study investigates how work-life balance practices impact employee outcomes such as job satisfaction, productivity, and well-being in multicultural work environments in Ghana. A cross-sectional study was conducted using an online survey of 336 participants from diverse cultural backgrounds across four regions in Ghana. The findings indicate that factors such as leadership support, flexible policies, fair compensation, training opportunities, and organizational culture significantly influence work-life balance, employee performance, and retention. Additionally, age, gender, income level, and marital status moderate this relationship. The results highlight the need for inclusive policies tailored to the unique needs of different demographic groups to enhance work-life balance. Fostering diversity, equity, and flexibility is ethically upright and strategically imperative for organizational success through improved employee outcomes. This study contributes empirical insights on managing work-life balance effectively across cultural contexts, aiding multinational organizations in supporting a global workforce.

INTRODUCTION

The growing complexities and competitiveness of the contemporary workplace, particularly the modern economy's demands for a productive and engaged workforce, have pressured enterprises to acclimatize to opportunities, changes, and challenges to survive (Madan et al., 2022; Rupčić, 2018). Consequently, organizations seek adaptive, innovative approaches to motivate their human resources. Work-life balance, a critical determinant of human resource well-being and organizational success (Bjök-Fant, 2023; Rashmi and Kataria, 2022), has thus become a highly pervasive concern for most businesses, as it is perceived to enhance employee performance. Work-life balance encompasses the fulfillment and effective functioning of individuals at both home and workplace levels, with little or no conflict between responsibilities (Mazerolle and Goodman, 2013).

However, work-life balance is argued to go beyond the primarily home and workplace spheres to cover aspects of personal development, community activities, nonpaying work, as well as leisure and recreation, implying that it includes the effectiveness with which individuals manage their work and non-work lives to their satisfaction (Bilge et al., 2021; Ten Brummelhuis and Van der Lippe,

2010; Stankevičienė et al., 2021). Notably, the globalization of business and the rise of multicultural work environments have transformed the traditional understanding of work-life balance (Chandra, 2012). Individuals from different cultural backgrounds bring unique perspectives, values, and expectations to the workplace,

influencing how they navigate the delicate equilibrium between professional responsibilities and personal life (Austin et al., 2007). As organizations strive to create inclusive and supportive environments, it becomes crucial to recognize and address the diverse needs and preferences of employees from various cultural backgrounds (Winfeld, 2014).

Research gap

Over the last few decades, work-life balance has drawn significant attention globally. Scholars note that it helps attract and retain employees while lowering work-life conflict and employee stress (Chaudhuri et al., 2020; Mordi et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Sánchez et al., 2020). Nevertheless, most previous studies in this field have focused on work-life policies and how they influence human resources within the organizational context. Many studies have also explored work-life balance from the perspective of gender in various human resource contexts, including the challenges women face in attaining work-life balance (Karkoulou et al., 2016; Lakshmi and Prasanth, 2018; Sundaresan, 2014). This study, however, recognizes the paucity of research on work-life balance from the perspectives of multicultural implications in an organizational setting (Oilier-Malaterre et al., 2013a, b). Amidst the imminent dearth of literature, Ajonbadi et al. (2023) allude to the limited understanding of how socio-cultural dynamics, social expectations, and coping mechanisms influence work-life balance perceptions and practices.

In the Ghanaian context, scholars have highlighted cultural nuances in various workplace experiences and practices, such as within Ghana's security industry (Amegayibor, 2023), the tertiary educational sector (Boakye et al., 2023), and among working mothers in urban Ghana (Abrefa Busia, 2023), providing valuable insights into the interplay between work-life balance and employee experiences in a dynamic cultural setup. Studies have also explored work-life balance among bankers in Accra (Darko-Asumadu et al., 2018) and female teachers (Edwards and Oteng, 2019). Further research has investigated the relationship between work-life balance and productivity (Ghareeb, 2019), as well as the experiences of university administrators (Obimpeh, 2021). According to Akanji et al. (2020), work-family balance holds more significance for women than men because women are exposed to more strenuous domestic responsibilities alongside workplace demands. Acheampong (2013), notes that many female Ghanaian lecturers reported declining or negative career progression due to family-work conflict. Similar observations were made by Appiah et al. (2014), who stated that family life commitments negatively impacted the careers and pursuit of further studies of Ghanaian female lecturers. Generally, scholars studying work-life balance have predominantly focused on Western countries, leading to less conceptualization of the phenomenon in Africa and other non-Western nations. The current study explores this phenomenon in a Ghanaian workplace context.

Study purpose and scope

Despite literature providing an empirical foundation for further investigating the nuances of work-life balance in Ghana's workplace environments, a comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay of cultural dynamics (values, societal expectations, and coping mechanisms) shaping how employees across different demographic groups perceive and manage their personal and professional realms is still lacking (Beauregard and Henry, 2009; Stankevičienė et al., 2021). Tackling these issues is critical for developing effective interventions tailored to the unique needs of Ghana's diverse workforce. Additionally, the literature lacks a detailed exploration of the interplay between cultural factors and work-life balance practices and their subsequent influence on employee outcomes (Beauregard and Henry, 2009; Rashmi and Kataria, 2022; Wood et al., 2020). The one-size-fits-all approach to work-life balance policies may be inadequate and inadvertently contribute to disparities and dissatisfaction among employees from different cultural backgrounds (Nwagbara, 2020). Cultural values, societal expectations, and individual coping mechanisms may significantly influence how employees perceive and

manage their work and personal lives, warranting a more in-depth investigation into the complexities of these interactions (Beauregard and Henry, 2009).

Research aim and objectives

The study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by investigating how work-life balance practices impact employee outcomes such as job satisfaction, productivity, engagement, and overall wellbeing in multicultural settings. Understanding the distinct difficulties and possibilities in diverse work environments is critical for developing successful strategies and measures that address the unique needs of individuals from different cultural perspectives. Hence, this study aims to investigate the impact of work-life balance on human resources, particularly focusing on outcomes such as job satisfaction, work productivity, and overall wellbeing within the multicultural setting of Ghana's workplace.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

This study explored how work-life balance impacts the multicultural workplace setting and influences workforce outcomes such as job satisfaction, work productivity, and overall well-being. A descriptive survey and a cross-sectional study design were adopted for this research. Being a qualitative study, the phenomenological approach was used to enable inquiry into the 'hows' and 'whys' of employees' interactions with the work-life balance phenomenon (Tarnoki and Puentes, 2019).

Study participants

Study participants included a sample of professional men and women with varied professional qualifications from select cosmopolitan cities in Ghana. The researchers used a convenience sampling method to select participants. Only willing individuals with relatively high commitment, role perception, and abilities within their respective professional environments were considered, resulting in a sample of 336 professionals.

Study area

As explained, cosmopolitan urban areas were chosen as the primary setting for this research due to the high density of dynamic professionals and the highly concentrated vital institutions and organizations that engage with high-, semi-, and low-skilled human resource teams. The representative research areas were the Western region, the Central region, the Greater Accra region, and the Ashanti region. These regions were also believed to exhibit greater diversity of men and women in the labor market. The study ran from October to November 2023, and participants were asked for written informed consent in electronic format (first pages of the data collection tool) prior to being recruited for the study.

Data collection instrument

A short and precise web-based, self-designed questionnaire was used as the data collection instrument, created using Google Docs (available at www.googledocs.form). The questionnaire comprised six segments. The first section inquired about participant demographic characteristics such as family status, academic qualifications, age and gender, present designation and professional rank, and work experience. Sections two to six consisted of open-ended questions designed to extract specific answers from respondents related to work-life balance metrics such as management and leadership experience, work-life conflict perceptions, performance, training and development, and satisfaction and compensation. A pilot study utilizing approximately 10% of the target population was conducted before the actual data collection. However, the data gathered during the pilot testing were not used for the main study to avoid introducing bias to the research.

Data collection procedure

A Google Forms web link containing the self-designed questionnaire was distributed among participants from the study area at the time of data collection. Participants aged 18 years and older were eligible to participate in the study. The survey link was sent via social media platforms, notably WhatsAppTM and LinkedInTM.

Statistical analysis

The collected data were evaluated for accuracy and completeness to address the research objectives. Subsequently, the data were exported into an Excel spreadsheet (Microsoft Excel 365®, 2016) for data cleaning, and further analysis was conducted using SPSS software (IBM SPSS® version 23). Frequency distributions, contingency tables, and various charts were employed to visually represent the analysis's findings, including descriptive and inferential statistics.

Descriptive statistics such as mean, percentages, and standard deviation were used to present participants' responses. Inferential statistics such as linear regression, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient, and chi-square analysis were conducted to derive meaning from the collected data. A p-value less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The survey results provided insights into the critical question fundamental to our research objective: How do work-life balance practices influence employee outcomes such as job satisfaction, productivity, engagement, and overall well-being in multicultural settings?

Descriptive statistics of study participants

Precisely 336 participants completed the online questionnaire survey. Among them, 62.5%, representing 210 participants, were males, while the remaining 126 (37.5%) were females, illustrating the relative predominance of men in the job market. The results also indicate a notable gender gap among the respondents, potentially limiting the range of perspectives and ideas regarding work-life balance in various institutions. Regarding age distribution, most participants (n = 78, 21.3%) were aged 21-25 years, followed by respondents (n = 62, 18.5%) aged 26 to 30 years. Additionally, 56

(16.7%) and 46 (13.7%) fell within the age groups of 36-40 years and 31-35 years, respectively, while only 6 (1.8%) participants were over 50 years old. The predominance of participants between the ages of 21-25 years and 36-40 years indicates an energetic workforce among various institutions. Regarding educational qualifications, the majority of respondents held a bachelor's degree (36.9%) or a master's degree (30.4%). Additionally, 15.5% held a doctoral degree, while 10.7% had a diploma qualification, and only 4.8% had a senior high school qualification. The prevalence of bachelor's or master's degrees among participants suggests a high level of education, facilitating meaningful conversations on complex subjects like work-life balance in a multicultural setting within various working groups in Ghana. Regarding job titles, a significant number of participants were professional staff (36.9%), followed by those in management roles (22.6%), entry-level employees (21.4%), and administrative support staff

(19%). Table 1 summarizes the distribution of sociodemographic characteristics among the study respondents.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics derived from the analysis of sociodemographic data from participants.

Variable	Frequency (n)	%
Gender		
Male	210	62.5
Female	126	37.5
Age/years		
18-20	40	11.9
21-25	78	21.3
26-30	62	18.5
31-35	46	13.7
36-40	56	16.7

41-45	34	10.1
46-50	14	4.2
>50	6	1.8

Educational qualification

SHS graduate	16	4.8
Diploma	36	10.7
Bachelor's degree	124	36.9
Master's degree	102	30.4
Doctoral Degree	52	15.5
Others	6	1.8

Job title

Administrative support	64	19
Entry level	72	21.4
Management role	76	22.6
Professional staff	124	36.9

N = 336.

Leadership and management play pivotal roles in enhancing work-life balance and positively influencing employee outcomes. Leaders who demonstrate a healthy work-life balance themselves convey a strong message to their staff. Additionally, effective leaders advocate for and implement policies that support flexibility, such as remote work options and flexible hours (McDonald et al., 2007). They communicate clearly about expectations, ensuring that employees understand their roles and can manage their time effectively, thereby reducing stress and promoting healthier work-life equilibrium (Marques and Berry, 2021). Moreover, proactive management practices are crucial for improving employee outcomes. Managers can foster open communication channels by regularly checking in with team members to assess workload and well-being (Ananthram et al., 2018). By providing ongoing feedback and recognizing achievements, managers contribute to a positive work environment that values individual contributions (Mone and London, 2018). Furthermore, supporting professional development and career growth opportunities demonstrates a commitment to employee success beyond immediate tasks (Dachner et al., 2021). A holistic approach to employee well-being, Paschina 87

Table 2. Work-life balance and employee outcome among the study participants.

Statement	Mean ± SD	95% CI	
		LL	UL

Exploring work-life balance and employee outcome

Questions (Table 2) designed to ascertain work-life balance and employee outcomes in a multicultural setting among the participants were partitioned into six sections: sections 1 (management and leadership), 2 (work-life balance), 3 (training and development), 4 (remuneration and satisfaction), 5 (performance), and 6 (turnover). Each section comprised five items. Questions in these sections were assigned values in a five-point Likert scale format (1 - strongly disagree, 2 - disagree, 3 - neutral, 4 - agree, and 5 - strongly agree). The mid-value, three (3), was chosen as an average value, indicating that scores below it were considered a poor response, and scores above it were considered favorable.

Leadership and management

Coupled with policies emphasizing flexibility and clear communication, ultimately improves work-life balance and positively impacts overall employee outcomes, including job satisfaction and performance (Tamunomiebi

and Oyibo, 2020). The findings from the present study (Table 2) are consistent with the works of Tamunomiebi and Oyibo (2020) and Guest (2017), whose results also revealed that managers' support for employees plays a substantial role in promoting work-life balance.

Perceptions of work-life conflict

The importance of work-life balance cannot be overstated when considering its profound impact on employee outcomes. Striking a balance between work and personal obligations is essential to building a happy and productive staff. Work-life balance is crucial for preventing burnout, reducing stress, and promoting overall well-being among employees. When individuals can effectively manage their time and energy, they are more likely to experience job satisfaction and remain engaged in their work. Employee outcomes, ranging from performance and productivity to job retention and job satisfaction, are intricately linked to the quality of work-life balance within an organization. When a balanced approach is used, it allows employees to take breaks and rejuvenate, which enhances their attention and inventiveness when they resume their professional responsibilities. On the contrary, a lack of balance can contribute to high levels of stress, fatigue, and decreased job satisfaction, potentially resulting in lower productivity and increased turnover rates.

Regarding questions on work-life balance, the respondents affirmed that there is a healthy balance between work and their personal lives, a finding consistent with the reports mentioned by Greenhaus et al. (2003).

Similarly, Koubova and Buchko (2013), in a study conducted to evaluate work-life balance among selected participants in corporate organizations, disclosed that the majority of the participants reported having a healthy balance between work and personal life. Despite the merits of doing so, some of the respondents (23%) highlighted that their organizations do not offer flexible working hours to accommodate their work-life balance. When this equilibrium is lost, people may suffer adverse effects on their personal and professional lives. When they are immersed in a constant cycle of work without sufficient time for personal pursuits or relaxation, they risk experiencing burnout, heightened stress levels, and a decline in overall well-being. Relationships might suffer, physical and mental health problems can arise, and work satisfaction can be negatively impacted by the unwavering pursuit of professional goals at the expense of personal life. Without a proper balance, individuals may find themselves trapped in a perpetual state of fatigue, diminishing their creativity, productivity, and overall effectiveness in the workplace (Dizaho et al., 2017). The lack of boundaries between work and personal life can result in a diminished quality of life, highlighting the importance of establishing and maintaining healthy work-life equilibrium for sustained individual and organizational success (Dizaho et al., 2017).

Training, development and performance

This sub-section explored the role of training and development in advancing work-life balance among the study participants. The summary of the responses obtained from the participants underscored that training and development may have a significant contribution to promoting work-life balance among employees. For example, a more significant number of the respondents (88%) showed that the training provided to the employees was adequate for their professional needs, which contributed to improving their work-life balance and performance. In the same way, those who participated confirmed that their company provides mentoring initiatives that help transmit expertise between generations. The forgoing findings were supported by the works of previous authors (Dizaho et al., 2017). Notably, (Dizaho et al., 2017) explored the application of intergenerational knowledge in promoting work-life balance; they underscored that those individuals in organizations that provide regular mentorship programs presented a significant chance of balancing work and personal life activities. These findings were also supported by the work of (Lambert et al., 2020). Although some respondents opined that training and development improved their work-life balance, most of the study participants reported that they could not balance their work and personal lives because training programs do not incorporate elements related to work-life balance.

Satisfaction and compensation

Satisfaction and compensation are integral to promoting work-life balance and influencing positive employee outcomes (Dizaho et al., 2017). When employees feel adequately compensated for their contributions, it creates a sense of value and recognition. Fair and competitive compensation provides financial stability and reduces stress related to economic concerns, allowing individuals to focus on their work and personal lives with a greater sense of security (Hoffmann-Burdzińska and Rutkowska, 2015). Consequently, this leads to increased work satisfaction among staff members who believe their contributions are valued and adequately compensated. Moreover, job satisfaction is pivotal in the overall work-life balance equation. A happy workplace and higher production result from engaged and devoted workers, who are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs. Policies and procedures that promote work-life balance, such as flexible work schedules, remote work choices, and wellness initiatives, are frequently put in place by companies that prioritize employee happiness. These programs help create a culture where workers feel appreciated for their contributions, not just in terms of pay but also in a supportive and respectful work environment that honors their personal life. Thus, the effective fusion of remuneration and pleasure serves as a potent deemed statistically significant stimulant for developing a well-rounded, happy, and productive staff. Conversely, findings from the present study disclosed that participants who reported poor job satisfaction and work compensation noted that these consequently affected their work-life balance and outputs.

Study findings on sociodemographic characteristics correlations

The effect of the socio-demographic characteristics of participants on the work-life balance outcomes of respondents was statistically assessed through a multilinear regression model. Table 3 summarizes the correlation analysis using multiple linear regression (MLR) models, with their corresponding standard error of estimate (SEE) and coefficients of determination (R^2), ascertaining the effect of sociodemographic characteristics on work-life balance and employee outcomes. The predictor variables included for this specific analysis were age, gender, work experience, income, religion, marital status, and educational background, while the dependent variable was noted as “work-life balance”.

Following the statistical analysis, it was reported that variables such as age ($p = 0.017$, $R^2 = 0.032$), gender ($p = 0.05$, $R^2 = 0.282$), income ($p = 0.032$, $R^2 = 0.671$), marital status ($p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.512$), and work experience ($p = 0.012$, $R^2 = 0.723$) were found to influence an employee’s work-life balance and outcome statistically. The results, however, did not show a statistically significant effect from independent factors such as educational background ($p = 0.231$, $R^2 = 0.112$) and educational background ($p = 0.312$, $R^2 = 0.219$) on employee work-life balance. The most significant variables that positively influenced employee work-life balance and performance were income, marital status, and work experience. This was attributed to the fact that the recorded coefficient of determination (R^2) was estimated to be above 50%. For instance, the coefficient of determination showed that 67.1, 51.2, and 72.3% of the variation in work-life balance and employee performance were influenced by a person’s income, marital status, and work-life balance, respectively. Although the educational background and work experience were not statistically significant, the coefficient of determination disclosed that an estimated 21.9 and 11.2% of the variation in the worklife balance of an employee was influenced by the educational background and the work experience of the employee, respectively. Work-life balance is greatly influenced by age, gender, income, and marital status, all of which have an impact on employee results. The varying life stages associated with age can shape an individual's priorities and commitments. Younger employees may prioritize career advancement and personal development, potentially leading to longer working hours, while older employees may seek a more balanced lifestyle, prioritizing family and personal wellbeing (King et al., 2012). Gender is a factor in societal expectations and traditional gender roles, affecting how individuals manage their

professional and personal lives (Ridgeway, 2009). According to Russell et al. (2009), income levels can impact access to resources that ease work-life conflicts, such as childcare or flexible work arrangements. Marital status introduces additional dynamics; for instance, single individuals might have more flexibility, while married individuals may need to balance the demands of both work and family. Employers looking to develop inclusive workplace policies supporting work-life balance and improving overall worker well-being and performance must consider these demographic characteristics.

Correlation analysis on main study variables influence employee outcomes at various organizations. Using an alpha level of 0.05 (at a 95% confidence interval), we observe that the MANOVA test produced a statistically significant result: Wilks' Lambda = 0.967, $F(4, 1190) = 5.105$, $P < 0.001$.

This significant F indicates significant differences among the "predictor variables" groups on a linear combination of the selected dependent variables. After obtaining a significant result for the MANOVA test, a univariate ANOVA test (Table 5) was conducted to examine workplace factors that can impact employee outcomes at various organizations.

Follow-up univariate ANOVAs indicated that workplace variables (such as leadership and management, work-life balance, training and development, satisfaction and compensation, performance, and turnover) were statistically significantly different for the employee outcomes; $F(4, 1190) = 5.370$, $P < 0.001$, multivariate η^2 (partial eta squared) = 0.281 and $F(4, 1190) = 4.685$, $P = 0.001$, multivariate η^2 (partial eta squared) = 0.316, respectively. The partial eta squared of 0.281 and 316 explains that only 28.1% and 31.6% of the multivariate variance in the dependent variable is associated with the group factor (employee outcome).

Conclusion

Recognizing and accommodating the diverse intersections of age, gender, income, and marital status are indispensable for fostering a healthy work-life balance and optimizing employee outcomes. Companies need to recognize that people go through different phases of life and that each one has its own goals and difficulties.

Organizations may foster a work-life balance by fostering gender equality, adjusting policies to meet the requirements of different age groups of employees, and taking financial inequality into account. Furthermore, being aware of the effects of marital status enables the creation of inclusive policies that consider employees' various family obligations. While some of the managerial practices suggested in this study, such as family-friendly policies and intergenerational mentoring, are already widely implemented, the quantitative results obtained provide new and relevant strategic insights into the Ghanaian context. In particular, demonstrating how demographic factors such as age, gender, marital status, and income level significantly moderate the relationship between work-life balance and outcomes for employees allows for the development of tailored recommendations for the Ghanaian workforce. These specific managerial implications, derived from the in-depth analysis of Ghana's socio-cultural complexities, represent an innovative contribution compared to studies conducted in other national or cultural contexts.

In the end, a workplace that respects and considers these demographic disparities improves worker happiness and well-being, productivity, performance at work, and organizational success. Embracing variety in work-life issues is a strategic necessity for developing a resilient and productive staff, in addition to being a caring approach.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

This study utilized the primary data collected from the online survey, and a structured questionnaire was utilized to collect data from the online respondents to minimize the chances of outliers. However, this was a significant weakness for this study since it posed biases in the data collected. The respondents were restricted on the type and amount of data to be provided. However, the researchers included appropriate data items in the questionnaire

design to enable complete and comprehensive information gathering based on the study objectives. Fundamentally, despite having a reasonably large sample size, there was a potential weakness of gender imbalance in the included samples. There were more male respondents than females, depicting the scenario of male dominance over females in the Ghanaian labour market. Despite being a weakness, this could reflect the ideal scenarios in most organizations in developing nations where employment opportunities and rights are unequal in various labor markets. To our disadvantage, male dominance is believed to enrich the discussion and findings in most factors, which potentially hinders its generalizability for the female gender. Finally, the entire dependence on qualitative methodology is limiting, especially in data collection, posing a danger to the integrity and reliability of the data collected. Such a study would benefit more from a mixed methodological approach of qualitative and quantitative paradigms.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Organizations and institutions ought to establish strong policy provisions for both the male and female genders to enhance work-life balance. For instance, the documentation, evidence and practical frameworks on work-life balance should inform the leadership. The focus should, however, be on the recognition and documentation of work-life balance initiatives towards the well-being of females due to their imminent neglect in most workplaces. Again, the ignorance and denial of work-life balance expected in most institutions and businesses should be eradicated, and identify and counter the cultural resistance that alienates the role and significance of women in a workplace environment. Business entities should also enact policies that champion workplace balance in every sector within the business processes and identify all potential bottlenecks that may hinder the full realization of WLB. Finally, administrative and leadership policies should highlight the consequences of non-compliance to work-life balance initiatives at each departmental unit or business level for large organizations.

OPPORTUNITIES FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This study raised some serious concerns that can be considered for future research. For instance, this study has more male than female representation; future research can focus on the balanced ratio of both genders to enhance representativeness and generalization of findings. Since, by default, the labour market opportunities for both women and men vary in developing nations such as Ghana, future research should explore work-life balance practices and exceptional cases to incentivize female employees amidst their limited spaces and recognition within the workplace setting. Further, future research should consider using a mixed methodology approach to enhance the reliability and rigor of the findings. Finally, the use of closed-ended questions as primary data sources limited information gathered from respondents. Utilizing face-to-face interviews with open-ended questions presents an excellent opportunity for researchers to gather more information on issues related to the labour market since it gives liberty to participants to clarify and give reasons for their responses.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

The author recommend family-friendly policies such as parental leave, childcare support, and eldercare assistance to optimize work-life balance and improve employee outcomes. These programs can help employees feel supported by their professional and personal duties and lessen the difficulties of having a family. Organizations should also create rules that address the various demands of staff members at various phases of their lives. A more welcoming and encouraging work environment may be created by offering mentorship programs to younger employees, offering older employees phased retirement alternatives, and providing ongoing chances for everybody to grow professionally. Improving work-life balance and worker satisfaction may require addressing gender-based inequities through equitable chances for professional progression, reducing wage gaps, and creating a diverse environment that questions established gender norms. This is advantageous to each person individually and a more inventive and diversified workplace.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The author has not declared any conflict of interests.

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